

Toxicity of Bisphenol-A: Effects on Health and Regulations

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Abstract : Bisphenol-A (BPA) is one of the highest volume chemicals produced worldwide in the plastic industry. This compound is mostly used in producing polycarbonate plastics that are often used for food and beverage storage, and BPA is also a component of epoxy resins that are used to line food and beverage containers. Studies performed in this area indicated that BPA could be extracted from such products while they are in contact with food. Therefore, BPA exposure is presumed. In this paper, the chemical structure of BPA, factors affecting BPA migration to food and beverages, effects on health, and recent regulations will be reviewed.

Keywords : BPA, health, regulations, toxicity

Conference Title : ICAFE 2014 : International Conference on Agricultural and Food Engineering

Conference Location : New York, USA

Conference Dates : June 05-06, 2014